

VETERINARY SCIENCES

POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS IN PATHOLOGIES OF THE URINARY SYSTEM IN DOGS

A. Yerkebulan,

Republic of Kazakhstan

«Aqtaban» veterinary center, Nurly lane 12, Astana

Zh. Kemeshev,

The S.Seifullin Kazakh agrotechnical university,

Republic of Kazakhstan

010011, 62 Zhenis avenue, Astana

D. Mussagiyeva,

The S.Seifullin Kazakh agrotechnical university,

Republic of Kazakhstan

010011, 62 Zhenis avenue, Astana

M. Alyonova

The S.Seifullin Kazakh agrotechnical university,

Republic of Kazakhstan

010011, 62 Zhenis avenue, Astana

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7300754>

Abstract

In the pancake and far foreign scientific literature, works devoted to the diagnosis and methods of treatment of animals with pathologies of the urinary system in animals are widely represented.

Keywords: Dog, bladder, endoscopy, diagnostic methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The relevance of the problem. Surgical pathologies of the urinary system are widespread in all species of animals. In their structure, special attention is paid to surgical pathologies of the bladder. This group of diseases primarily includes pathologies of metabolic (uro-lithiasis), traumatic, tumor nature, requiring surgical treatment. The available literature widely reflects the application of both classical and innovative methods for diagnosing surgical pathologies of the bladder. There is information on the use of computer and magnetic resonance diagnostics of cystopathies in small pets to verify the diagnosis (Liptak J.M., 2005; Barsanti J.A., 2006; Berent A., 2011; Chubarova E.A., 2012; Sobolev V.E., 2012; Kvochko A.N., 2016, Vatnikov Yu.A., 2019;). In foreign literature, the main information is presented in the works of Chew J.D., et al. 1996; Kruger J.M., 2003; Forterre S., 2004; Jacob F., 2005; Barsanti J.A., 2005; Childress M.O., et al. 2009; Berent A., 2011; Flatland B., 2010; Frazier D.L., 2011; Libermann S.V., 2011; Wiley J., 2016; Andrew R.E., et al., 2018; and other researchers. From the near foreign scientific literature, works devoted to the diagnosis and methods of treatment of animals with pathologies of the urinary system in animals are widely represented. It should be noted Russian researchers dealing with this problem: Medvedeva L.V., 2012; Chubarova E.A., 2012; Sobolev, V.E., 2012; Pozyabin, S.V., 2013; Goose, A.S., 2013; Shumakov N.I., 2014; Chernov, A.V., 2014; Lapshin, A.N., 2014; Vilkovsky, I.F. et al., 2015; Kvochko, A.N., 2016, 2018; Vatnikov Yu.A., 2019 and others.

According to Lapshin A.N. (2016), Pozyabin S.V. (2017), with classical access, postoperative complica-

tions often occur. One of the first is Peritonitis can develop due to the insolency of the suture on the wall of the bladder, as a result of which urine enters the peritoneal cavity and an extensive (diffuse) form of peritonitis develops. One of the first is Peritonitis can develop due to the insolency of the suture on the wall of the bladder, as a result of which urine enters the peritoneal cavity and an extensive form of peritonitis develops. This pathology is diagnosed by performing radiography, ultrasonographic examination, laparotomy, as well as laparocentesis, taking a sample of exudate of the peritoneal cavity, followed by cytomorphological and microbiological analysis. With laparotomy, the peritoneal cavity is washed with antiseptic solutions and drains are placed. With laparotomy, the peritoneal cavity is washed with antiseptic solutions and drains are placed. Also, postoperative fistulas are also not rarely formed - as a reaction of the body to a foreign body (Barde J.F., 1998; Morozov A.V., 2000; Kozlov E.M., 2002; Barsanti J.A., 2006; Brandt L.E., 2010; Brin M., 2015; Pozyabin S.V., 2017).

A fistula is a narrow channel lined with scar tissue through which inflammatory discharge spreads from the very focus of inflammation to the surface of the skin. The occurrence of fistulas leads to non-compliance with asepsis and antiseptics, as well as the body's response to suture material, i.e. inflammatory reaction around the filament (ligature). The thread is not encapsulated (there is no membrane of fibrous tissue), but a granuloma is formed, then an abscess, which leads to the formation and opening of the fistula. Most often, ligature fistulas arise from non-absorbable suture material. The classic method of treating fistulas is the excision of the entire fistulous passage, with its preliminary

staining with a solution of brilliant greenery and the focus of inflammation itself capturing the surrounding tissues (Kirk R., 2005; Inzhuvatova N.V., 2016). After incorrect transurethral cystoscopy, there is a risk of developing urethritis, while animals have pronounced vascularization of the walls accompanied by clinical signs (hematuria and difficulty urinating). Urethral stricture, according to Chernov A.V. (2014), can occur in chronic urethritis, after prolonged placement of a urethral catheter, traumatization of the mucous membrane with stones. The outflow of urine from the M.P. is restored by bougination with rigid urethral catheters, or balloon dilatation. More often, this pathology occurs in males due to the peculiarities of the anatomical structure. Insufficiency of the urethral sphincter is also a complication after prolonged catheter placement. Obstruction of the urethra occurs due to its blockage with stones. Due to the weak information content of the surgical reception of cystotomy, this pathology occurs in the postoperative period. It is eliminated by setting a urethral catheter and promoting uroliths into the bladder, or by using lithotripsy, which is performed using a laser. Stones with this technique are destroyed and come out along with the outflow of urine (Lavelle J.P., 2000; Brezis M., 2001; Brown S.A., 2009; Chew D.J., 2014; Lapshin A.N., 2014; Chernov A.V., 2014; Pozyabin S.V., 2017; Houston D.M., 2018).

Endoscopic methods for operations on the bladder in animals are the most informative and minimally invasive. The study of the bladder can be carried out through the external opening of the urethra (transurethral) or when performing laparoscopically assisted cystoscopy. There are several technical methods (methods) of endoscopic examination: - Transurethral cystoscopy is performed using a rigid endoscope with a diameter of 2.7 mm, or a flexible cystoscope of 3 mm.

Laparotomy-assisted cystoscopy is performed with a rigid endoscope of 2.7 mm. and 5 mm. Cystoscopy is performed for both therapeutic and diagnostic purposes, this, as a rule, a painless, minimally invasive, highly formative procedure. Indications for cystoscopy: detection of stones, neoplasms, bladder injuries, cystitis of various etiologies in the bladder. This technique allows you to assess the integrity of the walls of the bladder and urethra. When the bladder ruptures, surgical intervention is necessary, as it leads to peritonitis, and then to death (Morozov A.V., 2000; Vorontsov A.A. 2005; Medvedeva L.V., 2011; Worwag S, 2012; Lapshin A.N., 2016).

Neoplasms of the bladder and urethra occupy the second place among the pathologies of the genitourinary system and occur in both females and males, over the age of 6 years, they are usually represented by transitional cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, adenocarcinoma and rhabdomyoma (neoplasm of striated muscles). A distinctive feature of such neoplasms is the destruction of the basement membrane and infiltration by tumor cells of their own layer of the mucous membrane of the bladder. The first clinical sign of a neoplasm of the bladder is hematuria. The types of neoplasms and the degree of spread depend on many reasons. The fundamental difference in this case is

represented by superficial and invasive neoplasms. Superficial are characterized by the spread within the submucosal layer of the bladder wall. Such neoplasms grow inside the cavity of the bladder and very often connect to the wall with a thin leg, but they can also line the mucous membrane for a long time, which characterizes the picture of polypoid cystitis. Invasive neoplasms spread deep into the wall with infiltration of muscle layers and underlying tissues, which is characteristic of adenocarcinoma, leiomyoma, etc. (Morozov A.V., 2000; Liptak J.M., 2005; Kaney S, 2014; Pozyabin S.V., 2017).

References:

1. Barsanti J.A. and Finco D.R. Canine Prostatic Diseases. In: Textbook of Veterinary Internal Medicine, 4th edn, ed. S Ettinger and E Feldman, 2005. - pp. 1662-1685. WB Saunders, Philadelphia.
2. Behrend E.N., Grauer G.F., Mani I., Groman R.P. and Greco D.S. Hospital- acquired acute renal failure in dogs: 29 cases. Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association 2008. – p. 537-541.
1. Chew D.J., DiBartola S.P., eds., p. 29. Wilmington, NC: The Gloyd Group. Clanciolo RE, Bischoff K. Ebel JG. Van Winkle TJ, Goldstein RE, Serfilippi LM. Clinicopathologic, histologic, and toxicologic findings in 70 cats inadvertently exposed to pet-food contaminated with melamine and cyanuric acid. Journal of the American Veterinary Association. 2008. - 233 (5): 729 – 37.
2. Eric Monnet. Portosystemic shunts in dog and cats. College of Veterinary Medicine and Biomedical Sciences Colorado State University, Conference NAVC 2011, p.1422- 1425
3. Houston, D.M. Predisposition of different breeds to urolithiasis / D.M. Houston, A.-M. Germain // FOCUS. – 2018. - №9. – S. 46- 48.
4. Jacob F., Polzin D.J., Osborne C.A. et al. Evaluation of the association between initial proteinuria and morbidity rate or death in dogs with naturally occurring chronic renal failure. Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association. 2005. – p. 393-400
5. Peryshkina, L.S. Comparative characteristics of classical cystotomy and laparoscopically assisted cystoscopy in rabbits. /L.S. Peryshkina, S.V. Pozyabin // Scientific notes of the Kazan State Academy of Veterinary Medicine named after N.E. Bauman, 2019.- T.237.- P. 142-147.
6. Pozyabin, S.V. Methodology of laparotomy assisted cystoscopy in dogs. / S.V. Pozyabin, L.S. Peryshkina // Veterinary, zootechnics and biotechnology. 2017. - No10 - S.6-10.
7. Prober L.G., Johnson C.A., Olivier N.B., Thomas J.S. Effect of semen in urine specimens on urine protein concentration determined by means of dipstick analysis. American Journal of Veterinary Research. 2010. - 71: 288 – 92.
8. Stager, I.V. Frequency of occurrence and clinical manifestation of urolithiasis in domestic animals of the Republic of Khakassia. / I. V. Stager // Mezhdunarodnaya- issledovatel'nyi zhurnal. - 2017. №12 (66). S. 44-47.